

ULOGA STRUKTURNO-GEOLOŠKIH ANALIZA U ISTRAŽIVANJU HIDROTERMALNIH SUSTAVA – PRIMJERI IZ HRVATSKE

THE ROLE OF STRUCTURAL-GEOLOGICAL ANALYSES IN THE RESEARCH OF HYDROTHERMAL SYSTEMS – EXAMPLES FROM CROATIA

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APSTRAKT: Projekt „Multidisciplinarni pristup izradi konceptualnih modela hidrotermalnih sustava“ (HyTheC) koristio je strukturno-geološka istraživanja za stvaranje konceptualnih modela hidrotermalnih sustava na području Daruvara i Topuskog u hrvatskom dijelu Panonskog bazena. U Daruvaru su na temelju rezultata detaljne strukturne rekonstrukcije (terenski rad, daljinska istraživanja, virtualni izdanci, DFN modeliranje) procijenjeni hidrogeološki parametri te uspoređeni s podacima pokusnog crpljenja. Ova integracija potvrđuje vrijednost strukturnih istraživanja u predviđanju parametara toka. U Topuskom su strukturna-geološka istraživanja korištena za testiranje hipoteze o području napajanja. Novi strukturni profili poslužili su za postuliranje konceptualnog modela, dok su numeričke simulacije potvrdile njegovu valjanost. Oba slučaja pokazuju učinkovitost ove cjenovno prihvatljive metode za konceptualizaciju hidrotermalnih sustava. **Ključne reči:** hidrotermalni sustavi, strukturna geologija, pukotinski sustavi, numeričke simulacije, konceptualni modeli

ABSTRACT: The project „Multidisciplinary approach to conceptual modelling of hydrothermal systems“ (HyTheC) utilized structural geology to create conceptual models of hydrothermal systems in the Daruvar and Topusko areas of Croatian part of the Pannonian Basin System. In Daruvar, the hydrogeological parameters predicted through detailed structural reconstruction (fieldwork, remote sensing, virtual outcrops, DFN modeling) are compared to parameters calculated from pumping test data. This integration validated the structural approach for predicting flow parameters. In Topusko, structural field data is used to test the recharge area hypothesis. New cross-sections served to postulate the conceptual model, and numerical simulations confirm its plausibility. Both cases demonstrate the effectiveness of this cost-efficient method for hydrothermal system conceptualization. **Key words:** hydrothermal systems, structural geology, fracture systems, numerical simulations, conceptual models

INTRODUCTION

Pannonian part of Croatia has favourable geothermal characteristics and natural thermal water springs emerge at two dozen localities, with temperatures up to 65 °C (Borović et al., 2016). Thermal springs are part of hydrothermal systems which include: recharge areas in the mountainous hinterlands of the springs; geothermal aquifers (mostly Mesozoic carbonate rocks); and discharge areas in places with favourable structural characteristics of higher permeability. The continuous functioning of such systems depends on a delicate balance between groundwater flow velocities, precipitation/dissolution processes and structural framework. In order to maintain that balance and use thermal water resources in a sustainable manner, a system-level understanding is required. A five-year research project HyTheC uses multidisciplinary methodology (structural geology, hydrogeology, geothermal, hydrogeochemical and geophysical research and remote sensing) to construct conceptual models of systems. The methodology is tested in three pilot areas in Croatia and the results of the application of structural-geological analyses in two areas, Daruvar and Topusko, and for two different purposes, hydrogeological parametrisation and recharge area determination, respectively, are presented here.

METHODOLOGY

In the Daruvar pilot area the employed methods of structural-geological field research were measurements of the geometrical characteristics of strata bedding and fractures/joints (i.e., dip direction and dip angle); outcrop-scale structural data on fault geometrical properties, fault slip, and kinematics; and imaging of the outcrop analogue to obtain a 3D digital outcrop model (DOM). This was followed by digital structural analysis of the DOM reconstructing the main systems of discontinuities (i.e., both bedding and fractures), statistical analysis of the main geometrical parameters of the systems, and aquifer scale discrete

fracture network (DFN) modelling of the discontinuity network to assess the hydraulic parameters (i.e., porosity and permeability) of the model. Pumping test data were analyzed by different approaches and transmissivity, storativity, hydraulic conductivity anisotropy ratio, and the saturated thickness were obtained, to be compared to the estimation stemming from structural data (Kosović et al., 2024).

Structural-geological fieldwork in the Topusko pilot area involved structural and lithological data acquisition, focused on the contact types between lithostratigraphic units, geometrical and structural measurements of strata bedding, fractures/joint systems, and fault/shear planes, identification of the dip direction, dip angle, and strike of the planar and linear features, identification of fault's kinematic indicators and determination of tectonic transport of the cogenetic faulted structures. Collected structural data were used in the construction of three NE-SW striking regional structural-geological profiles. These profiles were used in the interpretation of the subsurface relations and the creation of a conceptual model which was then digitized, parametrized and numerical simulations of fluid flow and heat transport were conducted (Pavić et al., 2024b).

RESULTS

In the Daruvar test case the permeability calculated from the DFN model amounted to 59 D (calculated hydraulic conductivity of $9.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m/s), while the average value from pumping test data analyses was 89 D (or $1.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m/s). The examples from calculation processes are summarised in Figure 1.

Slika 1. Primjeri izračuna parametara iz DFN modela (lijevo) i podataka pokusnog crpljenja (desno).
Figure 1. Examples of parameter calculation from DFN model (left) and from pumping test data (right).

Pilot area of Topusko was structurally reinterpreted through three new cross-sections shown in Figure 2, and afterwards a conceptual model was constructed by combining information from the sections THS-2 and THS-3, digitized, parametrized and the simulations of the fluid flow and heat transport were run for periods of 100,000 years. An example of the result visualisation is shown in Figure 3. It can be observed that the isotherms of 60 °C reach the surface in the Topusko area, which physically verifies the proposed conceptual model with regard to heat transfer (temperatures of natural springs are in the range of 48-52 °C, and in the borehole up to 65 °C, Pavić et al., 2024a). Also, the outflow in the spring area was correctly simulated.

DISCUSSION

In the Daruvar pilot area results it is possible to observe that the obtained permeability (and calculated hydraulic conductivity) from different methodologies differ by an order of magnitude. This is the result of the necessary simplifications which had to be introduced to create the simplified model of a complex natural phenomenon. The simplifications are present in the calculation of hydrogeological parameters by both methodologies. The most important challenge in obtaining permeability from a DFN model was the lack of fracture aperture measurements, so the permeabilities were calculated for different realistic aperture values (0.1 – 4.1 mm). In the pumping test data analysis, the most important simplification, which was used also earlier in the research, was the consideration of Daruvar thermal aquifer as a quasi-homogenous porous medium at the investigated scale because it is heavily fractured (Borović et al., 2019).

Regarding the Topusko hydrothermal system, it was previously postulated that the recharge area of the system is west from Petrova gora nappe, where Jurassic and Triassic carbonates crop out, that the carbonate aquifers extend continuously below the nappe structure and, in the end, due to structural predispositions, the discharge area forms in the Topusko area east from Petrova gora Mt. (Šimunić, 2008). However, our structural measurements in the area have not given any basis to the claims that the Triassic carbonates could be extending below Petrova gora nappe, visible from the profiles in Figure 2. From those analyses we hypothesised that the recharge area is most probably from south and southwest where Triassic carbonates crop out and are heavily carstified, as evidenced from the high density of surficial landforms. Such conceptual model was physically verified through 2D numerical simulations (Pavić et al., 2024b). However, since the anticlines in the subsurface of this hydrothermal system shape a large dome-like structure, it is clear that the problem is three-dimensional, and will have to be modelled as such in the following steps. Considering this significant simplification of the system, the results of 2D numerical simulations have a very good fit the measured parameters.

CONCLUSIONS

Critical revision of the results and comparison of estimated parameters and previous knowledge in the Daruvar area lead us to consider the presented methodology applicable, but using due caution, especially if the data are scarce (which was not the case in our research, i.e. the data set was quite extensive).

In the case of Topusko hydrothermal system it is clear that gathering more structural data on the area was crucial in substituting the prevailing hypothesis on the recharge area of the system. Also, it enabled us the construction of a robust 2D conceptual model which was subsequently physically validated through numerical simulations.

Both presented examples highlight the fact that good quality and resolution of structural-geological data greatly improves the quality of conceptual models, especially regarding the possible recharge areas and estimating hydraulic parameters in case no wells are available for some systems, and therefore no state-of-the-art pumping tests can be performed. Also, it is clear that outcrop analogue imaging is quite cost effective and fast in comparison to structural measurements in the field, and certainly more economical than drilling well/s and conducting pumping tests. It implies that when we wish to physically validate the conceptual models of hydrothermal systems through numerical modelling, we can try to assess the hydraulic parameters of the aquifer using this cost-effective methodology, but also carefully considering the limitations.

Having good conceptual and numerical models of the hydrothermal systems enables both the delineation and protection of recharge areas and the determination of sustainable pumping rates, which is the prerequisite for long-term sustainable utilisation of hydrothermal systems, currently not adequately addressed in Croatian regulatory framework. The increase in thermal water utilisation is foreseen by many European and Croatian strategic documents regulating energetics, tourism and environmental protection. Therefore, we believe that in the future there will be need for these sample methodologies to be tested in different case-scenarios, which will lead to their further improvement.

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